

Eurodoc response to “European Research Area – the new ERA 4 years on: achievements, lessons learnt and the way forward”

Eurodoc's overall assessment of the ERA is positive. We find the ERA Forum and the ERA Actions suitable and effective platforms where the European Commission, Member States, Associated Countries, and stakeholder organisations can align their engagement, share their views, propose solutions, and identify factors hampering the development of a European Research Area. For this reason, we urge the ERA Forum to further strengthen the possibility of all relevant stakeholders to engage.

It is imperative that the next work program for the ERA builds on the previous one. In particular, a strong focus on Sustainable Research Careers and Research Assessment, Open Science and Equity Access to Research Infrastructure, Gender equality and Equal Opportunities, Fundamental Research, Trust in Science, Research Integrity and Ethics, and Scientific Freedom must remain at the core of the next cycle ERA-Actions. These topics are at the core of the research and innovation sector and directly link to the fundamental values of European democracy.

The next work program of the ERA should furthermore ensure cohesion across the different initiatives; the ERA Actions should specifically take up structural topics, such as those mentioned above. Whereas more thematic or specialised concerns should rather be addressed through Horizon Europe (HEU) with designated calls and allocated resources. Last but not least, it needs to be stressed that Europe is still lagging behind its competitors regarding investment in Research and Innovation, especially in comparison with the US and China, with the stated goal of 3% of the EU member states GDP for R&I investments still far from being a reality.

Importance of the ERA and the Stakeholder Forum

Eurodoc wants to stress **the importance and the success of the co-creative process for the ERA** in drafting the policies, ensuring joint priorities, as well as providing a good understanding of the diverse challenges faced ‘on the ground.’ We sincerely hope that this co-creative approach will only be strengthened, ensuring the inclusion of all relevant stakeholders, particularly Stakeholder Group 4 (Researchers and Innovators), for the diversity of their crucial insights that they bring to the table, thereby further increasing the effectiveness of the ERA. For doctoral candidates, postdocs, and other early career researchers (ECRs), ERA has been impactful particularly in its emphasis on the importance and need of ensuring sustainable career structures for researchers, and particularly so for those early in their careers.

While some actions in the ERA policy agenda 2021-2024 have been exemplary in fostering dialogue between the European Commission, Member States/Association Countries, and stakeholder organisations (such as Action 5), others failed to live up to the full potential of including the expertise of stakeholder organisations. Like others, Eurodoc believes that the ongoing ERA Action 6 (academic freedom) and Action 16 (access to excellence) would have benefited significantly by a more systematic inclusion of stakeholders such as research-performing and -funding organisations, researchers, and their respective associations.

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‘The Fifth Freedom’ – the Freedom of Knowledge

Knowledge, the circulation of knowledge, innovation, and education are crucial for the success of the single market. A key element of the movement of knowledge are doctoral candidates, postdocs, and other ECRs. The importance of ‘the fifth freedom’ for the EU (that is the “free movement of knowledge in the single market”) necessitates fundamentally the improvement of the conditions under which doctoral candidates, postdocs, and other ECRs move within the single market. Particularly where they lack worker status, doctoral candidates and postdocs face challenges or are forced to take risks, not least in regards to social security benefits and pensions. Ensuring that all research workers hold the EU-juridical **worker status, including transversal access to social security benefits**, would ensure a solid foundation for the promotion of the free movement of knowledge in the EU, including of researchers themselves.

Researcher careers are highly unpredictable and casualisation is increasing. The work toward a reform of researcher careers (such as CoARA) that has been begun in recent years is crucial, but clearly needs to be intensified to improve equitable access to researcher careers (e.g. for female researchers, for researchers with disabilities, for researchers from disadvantaged communities) and the retention of the best-qualified researchers for HEIs. In particular, we are still far from making “the guarantee of proper conditions for research employment” a reality. Such conditions of precarity are not equally affordable for all talents: ensuring the attraction and retention of talent for research, innovation, and higher education is thus contingent on the creation of sustainable research careers. Otherwise the realisation and the quality of the ‘fifth freedom’ will remain on precarious grounds itself.

The lack of sustainability in research detrimentally impacts its quality: it forces researchers to focus on short-term projects for immediate job security, it limits their ability to engage in long-term innovative research, and it increases turnover, leading to a loss of expertise and continuity within research teams.

As Open as Possible

The ERA should intensify its efforts for improving the implementation and monitoring of open science at all levels (European, national, and institutional) by promoting the use of reusable high-quality research data through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and by promoting the “Swedish May 2023 Conclusion” that called for a scholarly publishing model that is not-for-profit, open access, and multiformat, making research results more accessible and useful. The new ERA work program should however put a stronger focus on equity in open science to ensure that equity is at the core of OS. In all its activities, the ERA should remain true to the core principle of Open Science “as open as possible,”

The Continuation of the Current Action 5 – Gender Equality

Gender equality and equitable opportunities must remain a focus of the next ERA work program. However, it is fundamental that the work is expanded and takes on an intersectional approach. Furthermore, improvement is necessary in regards to monitoring and evaluation mechanisms of national dynamics in regard to policies on gender equality, mainstreaming, and intersectionality

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to gain a detailed picture of gains as well as setbacks at European and national level. Gender equality plans should not only remain mandatory to access EC funds (ERC, Framework Programmes, HEU, etc), their implementation needs to be strengthened including legal compliance checks of the GEP eligibility criterion. Moreover, a specific focus on the conditions of ECRs should be added. The increased competitiveness at European and global level risks exacerbating the deep inequalities that already exist in academia and exacerbates the vulnerability of this group.

Improving Access to Excellence

The next ERA work plan should continue to work towards ensuring that there are no two-tier systems across the research area. The creation of schemes for brain-gain in the Widening countries could be an effective tool, especially by supporting HEIs in the creation of attractive, forward-looking and sustainable employment and career structures. Without researchers there can be no research - and adequate working conditions and sustainable research careers across the EU and in candidate states will be increasingly essential for the retention of talents within Europe and to attract talents to Europe.

Unfortunately, over the previous framework programmes, the disparities in performance among EU member states has not been significantly reduced. The European Research Area can only be achieved if national R&I systems are competitive and mutually compatible, as well as by creating effective synergies within and between European programmes. The “Widening Participation and Spreading Excellence” must remain a central pillar in the upcoming work program of the ERA, a special focus should furthermore be paid to the strengthening of the Ukrainian higher education and research sector.

Deepening the ERA

The fundamental values of the European Union and democracy should be at the core of the deepening of the ERA. Both academic freedom within Europe and the participation of the academics in the governance of the ERA – notable as stakeholders in the ERA - Forums need to be essential pillars here. Over the course of the last years, the importance of strengthening public trust in science, science communication and outreach, has become more acute, not least in light of the proliferation of dis- and misinformation and other societal challenges. The upcoming work program for the ERA should reflect this. This work equally needs to include all relevant stakeholders – including researchers – to be effective.

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Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 24 national associations of early career researchers (ECRs) from 22 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research, higher education, and innovation in Europe.

